

URBAN HEALTH DELIVERY SYSTEM: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON CHENNAI CORPORATION

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Abstract

Population rapidly increasing in India particularly in urban areas. Chennai is the Capital of Tamilnadu and one of the oldest Municipal Corporations and fourth largest Metropolitan City in India. The Chennai city has a large migrant population with labourers living in slums. The increasing population concentration in slums has elicited a strong interest in urban sanitary conditions in general and the health of slum dwellers and the urban poor. The Government of TamilNadu and Chennai Municipal Corporation concentrated to improve the health conditions. This paper explores the various health delivery system and its impact on health welfare activities. and also identifies the measures to on enhance the health problems in Chennai.

Key words: Heath Administration, Urban Health, Health Delivery System

INTRODUCTION

Tamil Nadu is known for its impressive achievements in the health sector. A dynamic Public Health system, the State's emphasis on the Primary Health Care and Promotive Health, well trained and skilled human resources, efficient drug distribution system, state of art secondary and tertiary care, unique, innovative and targeted schemes, a robust Public Private partnership through the Insurance sector are some of the several reasons which have been attributed as the reasons for the State's success in health care.¹

In 1923, Government formed a separate Directorate exclusively for Public Health and named as The Directorate of Public Health and Preventive Medicine, which makes Tamil Nadu, the first State to have a separate Directorate for Public Health.² The Department's objective is to prevent disease, prolong life and promote health through organized measures. The prime functions of Public Health department include health promotion through healthy behaviour, prevention and control of Communicable and NonCommunicable diseases, provision of community based Maternity and Child Health Services including Immunization and Family Welfare Services. It also monitors the health needs, trends at community level through surveillance of diseases and risk factors.

The Department of Public Health and Preventive Medicine provides the Primary Health Care services in the State through 1,830 Primary Health Centres (PHCs) (including 424 Upgraded Primary Health Centres) in rural areas, 347 Urban Primary Health Centres in urban areas and 140 Urban Primay Health Centres in Greater Chennai Corporation to achieve quality services and Health for All.³ There are 8,713 Health Sub Centres (HSCs) functioning in the State as first level of service delivery units to provide Primary Health Care in rural areas and 1,643 Urban Health Sectors in urban.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Health is fundamental to quality of life. All human beings have an equal right to health. Health policy, health promotion and education, health care, and health care services are means to ensure this fundamental human

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right. They have to protect and improve the health of the community, from birth to death, in a preventive way and, if need be, in a curative or even in a palliative way.

As consumers of health care, which is inherently person-centred by nature, patients have to preserve the fundamental human right of self-determination. Patients have a right of access to health care (at least at basic or emergency levels), right to considerate care, right to informed consent and the right to information concerning the health services available.

Within a global health policy, governments should guarantee the existence of a health care system providing equal, accessible, comprehensive, and high-quality care to all at a reasonable cost, according to the economic situation of the nation. A health care system may belong to public and/or private sectors. Policy making should be a response to the accurately assessed health needs of the population.⁴

Planning of health care services involves identifying adequate criteria for a better distribution of health care, human resources, infrastructure, and medical technology, taking into account demography and epidemiology. Health has been a prime concern of humanity since the dawn of history. Some of the earliest written records refer to the struggle against disease and to the contrast between the factors that made for a long and healthy life and those that made life short and harsh.⁵

Today we have the knowledge of tools to prevent many diseases. We know how to improve our health and how to give ourselves, our families, and our communities the best possible chance of staying healthy.

The World Health Organization was created in 1948, with the ultimate aim of making possible the attainment by all people of the highest possible level of health – not merely the absence of disease but health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being.

Health for all does not mean, however, that sickness and disability will be conquered or that sickness and disability will be conquered or that technically advanced medical care means that health begins at home, in schools and at factories. It does mean that essential health care will be accessible to all individuals and families in an acceptable and affordable way and with their full involvement.⁶

For that primary health care was identified and it is considered as the key to attaining the social target of health for all. The Declaration of Alma-Ata defined primary health care as, “essential health care based on practical, scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community through their full participation and at a cost that the community and the country can afford to maintain at every stage of their development in the maintain at every stage of their development in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination. It forms an integral part of both the country’s health system, in which the social and economic development of the community bringing health care as close as possible to where people live and work and constitutes the first element of a continuing health care process.⁷

URBAN HEALTH INITIATIVE

It is estimated that India’s urban population of around 320 million is one of the largest in the world. The urbanization process in India and other parts of the world constitute a major demographic issue of the 21st century.

In absolute numbers, the urban population has increased 8 times in the last 50 years, from 44 million to 320 million. The pace of urban growth in India was high during 1951-91; the number of towns increased from around 2,843 in 1951 to approximately 5,100 in 2001. The number of cities with over one million populations has nearly doubled since 1980, from 12 to 23, with the urban population rising from 26.8% to over 35%. Urban India has four mega-cities (population over 5 million), 19 metro cities (>1 million), 3,000 large towns (> 0.1 million), and 3,396 small and medium towns (less than 0.1 million). Urban India has 25.7% of the national population, one of the largest urban systems in the world. At the national level, trends indicate that while rural poverty is declining, urban poverty is increasing.⁸

It is difficult to estimate the poor and slum population living in urban areas. Thus the actual facts about the urban poor, especially relating to their health and nutritional status, remain hidden. Between 39-43% of India's slum population is distributed in the metropolitan cities of Calcutta, Mumbai, Delhi and Chennai.⁹

The health of the urban poor is influenced by the urban economy, urbanization and urban environment. Major problems related to the environment are: unhygienic accommodation, inadequate water supply, sanitation and solid waste disposal, rights over land tenure, inadequate food supplies and the increasing demand for employment and social services. Health problems among the urban poor are determined by three main groups of factors, namely:

- poverty-related problems such as: unemployment, low income, limited education, inadequate diet, malnutrition;
- environmental problems leading to communicable and infectious diseases;
- Non-communicable disease burdens like accidents and psychological problems such as stress, alienation, instability and insecurity, leading to depression, smoking, and drug addiction. Major challenges are in the field of environmental sanitation, provision of safe drinking water and access to health care facilities. These concerns need initiatives at the regional, state and national level with clear programs and plans for evaluation.¹⁰

Currently, there is paucity of well-described data on various health issues in the urban population such as slum versus non-slum, the underprivileged and street children. Access to health, utilization patterns, and morbidity and mortality dynamics have not been delineated. Data are needed to assess the health needs, perceptions on health, healthcare providers and feasible interventions to reduce the morbidity, increase access to care and provide high-quality care. The proposed study will gather information in these areas.¹¹

It is in this context this proposed study has been undertaken.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Population and Human Wellbeing, World Resources Institute, it is estimated that urban population is growing four times faster than rural population in the world (Krishnamurthy M 2005). Out of the 59 urban agglomerations 23 mega cities in the world will have more than 10 million populations by 2015 as per the UN population estimate of 1999. According to Census of India (2001), 285 million (27.8%) of the 1027 million populations are in the urban and peri-urban areas. About 30% of these urbanites are migrants from rural population. 61% of the urbanites migrate within the cities/ towns. 60% of the urban people are below poverty line and are forced to live in the congested and unhealthy slums/jugghi zopadas favorable to continued transmission of leprosy disease. Census 2001 of India also identified the following two types of urban areas.¹²

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to understand the functioning of urban health care delivery system in Chennai city. Besides, it has the following objectives

- To specify various urban health delivery services,
- To analyze the causes for the poor performance of urban health care delivery system.
- To understand the level of health awareness among the urban population, with special reference to Chennai.
- To suggest various measures for effective delivery of urban health services

METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

The method adopted for the study is descriptive and analytical. Primary source of data were collected from a sample of 150 respondents hailing from various localities in North Chennai Municipal area. The respondents were chosen on simple random basis and interviewed through a structured schedule. Interview Schedule has been applied to elicit information regarding the performance of health delivery system in Chennai Municipal Corporation. The data collected have been systematically arranged, analyzed and interpreted through a master chart.

PEOPLE'S PERCEPTION

Public health system is a social system consisting of mechanisms and organized efforts of a society or nation to protect promote and restore people's health. Its three major components are:

- Organizations such as Ministry, Department, Executive Directorate, Educational and Research institutions, Service Delivery institutions such as health manpower, health care infrastructure, hospitals etc.
- Health management consists of systematic planning, programming, implementing, monitoring and evaluating, redesigning and upgrading in order to meet the ever changing and dynamic health status and challenges.
- The people for whose health and welfare, the system exists and expected to work. Public health also has inevitable relationship with other social, economic and political systems.

Hence, an attempt has been made in this chapter to analyze the public perception of the health system in Chennai Municipal Corporation.

Table – 1 Table Showing Respondent's Satisfaction about Urban Health Centers in their Locality

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Satisfactory	93	62.00
2	To Some Extend Satisfactory	33	22.00
3	Not Satisfactory	24	16.00
Total		150	100.00

The health infrastructure available in India may not be totally satisfied all citizens. for various reasons such as inadequate health personnel, lack of modern facilities, known availability of medicines etc. However, urban centers like Chennai particularly urban health centers maintained by Chennai Municipal Corporation are well equipped. As such 62 percent expressed satisfaction over the functioning of health facilities available in their locality. Similarly, 22 percent respondents are to some extend satisfied with such facilities. Only 16 percent are dissatisfied the urban health centers in the study area.

Table – 2 Table Showing Respondent's View on Availability of Medicines and Drugs

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Available	104	69.33
2	Not Available	46	30.67
Total		150	100.00

The above table shows that the availability of medicines in urban health centers. It clearly indicates that 69.33 percent respondents are accepting the fact that necessary medicines and drugs are available. And the remaining 30.67 percent are expressing that adequate medicines and drugs are not available in the urban health centers situated in their localities.

Table – 3 Table Showing Reason for Admission in Urban Health Centers

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Admitted for Delivery and women related	42	28.00
2	Minor Treatment	69	46.00
3	Other Reasons	39	26.00
Total		150	100.00

The above table clearly indicates the fact that more number of persons i.e., (46 percent) have been admitted in Urban health centers for taking minor treatments such as small injuries, fever, and so on. Another 28 percent respondents, all of them are women mostly admitted for delivery related reasons. The remaining 26 percent respondents are going to urban health centers eager for consultancy or referral services.

Table – 4 Table Showing Quality of Treatment in Urban Health Centers

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
	Very Good	58	38.67
	Good	44	29.33
	Satisfactory	31	20.67
	Not Satisfactory	17	11.33
Total		150	100.00

Respondent's response towards quality of treatment available in urban health centers seems to be mixed one. As the above facts show that 38.67 percent respondents feel that quality of treatment and services enjoyed by them are very good. Similarly another 29.33 percent also opine that the services available in urban health centers are good. 20.33 percent respondents said that the quality of treatment is satisfactory. Only the remaining 11.33 percent respondents felt that the services are not satisfactory.

Table – 5 Table Showing Satisfaction of the Respondents towards Health Awareness Programmes

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Satisfactory	97	64.67
2	Not Satisfactory	36	24
3	Do not know	17	11.33
Total		150	100.00

Both the central and state government's health departments are implementing various health awareness programmes like, AIDS awareness, Immunization, Polio Vaccination, etc., these awareness programmes are much useful for the people told know about health programmes in urban health centers. In these regards 64.67 percent respondents are satisfied with the health awareness programmes through which they know about the on going health programmes. 24 percent respondents are not at all satisfied with such awareness programmes. Another interesting fact is that 11.33 percent are not knowing about such awareness programmes which show their apathy.

Table – 6 Table Showing Reasons for Poor Performance of Urban Health Centers

Sl. No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
	Over Crowded	72	48.00
	Lack of Quality of Service	34	22.67
	Shortage of Personnel	14	9.33
	Lack of Infrastructure	30	20.00
Total		150	100.00

Generally it is opinioned that governmental hospitals are not effectively treating the patients and providing satisfactory services to the needy people. Because of various reasons 48 percent respondents feel that over crowded is the main reason for poor urban health delivery services. 22.67 percent respondents are indicating lack of quality of service is another reason for poor performance of the government urban hospitals. Lack of infrastructure and shortage of personnel also have impact on the delivery of services.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Developing countries like India are still struggling to expand their health infrastructure and provide basic health facilities to the entire population. If India is to progress towards equity, equality, radical institutional reforms in the health sector are needed. Providing mechanisms for the delivery of essential cost-effective quality care is a government responsibility and, of necessity, requires a strong and sustained political will. The potential advantage from restructuring health care is that can be extended to those who need it most.

Recent experience of developed countries suggest that investment in decentralized population-based systems and health service research aimed at the developing evidence-based health care, rather than the emphasis on central, disease-based systems could yield substantial health gains for the population.

The health services would be expected to be responsive to the needs of all; cost-effective and affordable, and of high quality; humane, caring, and culturally acceptable; innovative in provision of services.

The health sector therefore needs radical institutional reforms-in particular, improvement in functioning of public bureaucracies and a diversified approach to health services delivery. The objective India is striving towards with such reforms is to increase basic health services to underserved populations in the context of limited institutional capacity. While restructuring the health services, emphasis does, however, need to be on decentralized decision-making, universal accessibility and coverage, self-reliance, inter-sectoral action for health, use of appropriate technology, consideration of cost-effectiveness in relation to the available resources, and establishing of sound infrastructure. Emphasis is being given to raising awareness about health and enhancing public participation.

Hospitals and primary health care services are equally important links in a modern health system. The primary health care offers a broad spectrum of professional and flexible services, very close to the patient and his family. Hospitals are the key element in any health care system. Being centres of specialized medicine and technology, with large multidisciplinary teams, these institutions deliver a whole range of specialized services. Availability of health care facilities is one of the basic needs of people. In a big country like India, the responsibility of the government is onerous since a large section of the population is below the poverty line. Therefore, their dependence on government owned and managed health care institutions are total. (The term health care institutions have been used in this article as a generic term to include all types of institutions dealing with health care services, directly or indirectly).

FINDINGS

- our respondents coming from all the socio-economic categories. As such 62.67percent are male and the remaining 33.33 percent are women. Thus it seems that urban health infrastructure is mostly used by male respondents then the women respondents. Women mostly prefer private clinic for health problems like pregnancy and etc.
- All the age groups are coming to the urban health centers for taking treatment for their diseases or health problems. Among the respondents, those belonging to 41-60 are higher in number which means they often visit the urban health centers followed by the age group 26-40
- The education level of the respondents reveals the fact that low level educated respondents are visiting the urban health centers, i.e., 42.67 percent, followed by secondary level educated respondents, i.e., 23.33 percent.
- Accessibility of health facilities in urban health centers are mostly coming from wage employment groups, i.e., 61.33 percent followed by respondents engaged in business activities, which is 21.33 percent
- All the communities of the respondents are found in the beneficiaries of urban health infrastructures
- Respondents belonging to low income group use the urban health centers more often than the other income group level.

- As such 62 percent expressed satisfaction over the functioning of health facilities available in their locality. Similarly, 22 percent respondents are to some extent satisfied with such facilities. Only 16 percent are dissatisfied the urban health centers in the study area.
- 69.33 percent respondents are accepting the fact that necessary medicines and drugs are available. And the remaining 30.67 percent are expressing that adequate medicines and drugs are not available in the urban health centers
- More number of persons i.e., (46 percent) have been admitted in Urban health centers for taking minor treatments such as small injuries, fever, and so on
- 38.67 percent respondents feel that quality of treatment and services enjoyed by them are very good. Similarly another 29.33 percent also opine that the services available in urban health centers are good. 20.33 percent respondents said that the quality of treatment is satisfactory
- 64.67 percent respondents are satisfied with the health awareness programmes through which they know about the on going health programmes. 24 percent respondents are not at all satisfied with such awareness programmes.
- 48 percent respondents feel that over crowded is the main reason for poor urban health delivery services. 22.67 percent respondents are indicating lack of quality of service is another reason for poor performance of the government urban hospitals. Lack of infrastructure and shortage of personnel also have impact on the delivery of services.

SUGGESTIONS

Health care services are both highly specialized and very complex. In each department of specialization there must be a manager to coordinate and direct those services within and between departments. There also needs to be a manager who direct the overall organization and coordinate its efforts with other health care organization. There are also agencies responsible for managing the health care system in total community health care systems. Modern health care management concerns include an emphasis on increased efficiency, the meeting of administrative challenges and the development of behavioral insights.

New technology and the expansion of scientific knowledge coupled with evidence – based medicines have resulted in changes in the way care and other services are provided. Persistent and increasing unemployment is leading to more poverty and poor health. There is a universal trend towards greater decentralization and rapid expansion of the private health sector, introduction of charges to users and purchaser provider splits.

National health policy needs to be formulated with particular emphasis on long term and comprehensive strategies, attention to macro – economic efficiency based on the real health needs of the population equity of access and financial burden, balance on going specialization with the development of health care sector, encourage substitutability among health groups and facilitate the role of the family and the community. An essential requirement is a coherent link between national goals and strategy and implementation at the local level. This will enable achievements of national policy and establish a frame work for managing change in the local health system.

Although organizing quality care for all citizens is a responsibility of the government, the public have important responsibilities. The governments should assume leadership in initiating and managing changes within their health systems and their application to the health of the community.

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